

PRIVACYLANDIA

GAME INSTRUCTIONS

INTRODUCTION

This is a role-based game where different players take the role of the inhabitants of a fictional town. Each player needs to collaborate with at least another player and uses her/his knowledge in legal and technological domains to solve problems which an individual being data subject may face in real life.

PLAYERS

At least 6 participants to be grouped into teams of minimum 2 players; the game is recommended for scholars, professionals, and students with expertise in law and/or technological fields.

THE BOARD

A3 (210 x 297 mm) color printed playground with different paths and challenges.

ACCESSORIES

1 dice

6 pawns

6 printed role cards

printed (50,5 x 83,5 mm) challenge cards: Tier 1 (Green), Tier 2 (Blue), Tier 3 (Red),

printed bonus cards: Tier 1 (120 x 62 mm), Tier 2 (127 x 67 mm), Tier 3 (140 x 77 mm)

printed penalty cards: 110 x 80 mm

DURATION

Recommended time is 1 hour, unless none of the teams reaches the FINISH before time lapse. In that case, the ranking will be done based on the points collected by each team up to that point.

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TEAM CONSTRUCTION

TEAMS

Each player should declare from the beginning the team he/she would like to form/join. Each team contains minimum 2 members (one with legal and one with technical expertise).

The team members may collaborate with each other during the game. Points collected by each member are summed up in the final ranking that will decide the winning team. The goal of the game is not simply reaching the FINISH first but collecting the most points possible. Team members may solve all the challenges together and hence gain more points – difficult challenges may assign bonuses to each member of the team.

PERSONAS:

Before starting the game, each player selects a role card (“Persona”) that will be attributed to them during the whole game. Each persona has certain characteristics and skills related to certain fields on the game or certain challenges. Personas bring two types of advantages: field advantage (when a player stops on the field which corresponds with their persona gets a bonus) and expertise advantage (when a player solves the challenge question which corresponds with their persona gets a bonus).

Persona	Field Advantage	Expertise advantage
Doctor	1 extra point if he/she stops in the Hospital and Pharmacy field	+1 extra point for any challenge solved.
Lawyer	1 extra point if he/she stops in the Court and Police Station field	+1 extra point for any IT-related challenge solved.
Researcher	1 extra point if he/she stops in the University and Library field	+1 extra point for any RED challenge solved.
IT developer	1 extra point if he/she stops in the Internet provider, Telecom provider and Digital Platform field	+1 extra point for any legal-related challenge solved.
Student	1 extra point if he/she stops in the Social Network, Streaming Service and Gym field	+1 extra point for any GREEN challenge solved
Entrepreneur	1 extra point if he/she stops in the Bank and Post Office field	+1 extra point for any BLUE challenge solved.

START

The game starts from the START field.

To decide the order, each player will launch the dice; whoever gets the higher number will go first. In the case 2 or more players get 6, they will launch the dice once again until the order is defined.

GAMEPLAY

The players in turn launches the dice and moves the pawn on the board according to the number on the dice (from 1 to 6).

There is no predefined direction to be followed: it can be played clockwise or counterclockwise.

The game ends when each member of the team reaches the FINISH, hence every player of the team may decide to move in the same or different direction with the other team members.

The goal of the game is to reach the FINISH with the highest points possible.

There are different LOCATION FIELDS, ACTIONS FIELDS and CHALLENGES in the path (inspired from real-world scenarios) which require a certain action. This may influence the “community” as a whole or one specific player/team.

The challenges will have different levels of difficulties (Green – Low, Blue – Medium, and Red – High) and might involve other entities as well.

When the player is positioned in a challenge field, he/she will randomly extract one card of the same color from the deck of challenge cards.

The player will read the challenge described in the card to the community.

The “solution” to the challenge may be first discussed within the team or directly presented to the community and its outcome is evaluated by the other players. If the other players are satisfied with the proposed solution, the player (and his/her team members in some cases) will gain the specified bonus that can be used later in the game or given to another player/team member at any time or when he/she is asking for support. If one or more players are not satisfied with the proposed solution, they need to provide an explanation for their disagreement, and may suggest / recommend some elements that should have been included / discussed as part of the solution.

Other team members may decide to intervene/help solve the challenge or decide not to be involved.

If the majority of the other players (community) decide the solution is not satisfactory, the player (and his/her team on some occasions) will gain a penalty (based on the difficulty level of the challenge).

If a player is never engaged in discussions around the challenges (e.g., does not express his/her approval of or disagreement with the proposed solution, does not volunteer to help his/her team members, etc., he/she will be penalized by the other players. Again, the penalty will be decided by the community. The goal of the game is to promote collaboration and engage as much as possible, not to be indifferent.

TRANSITION: The orange wall dividing the two levels cannot be passed – the player must reach the TRANSIT cell and PAY the specified number of points to reach the second level.

LOCATION FIELDS:

Bank

Clothing store

Coffee shop

Court

eShop

Digital platform

Gym

Hospital

Internet provider

Library

Pharmacy

Police station

Market

Municipality

Social Network

Streaming service

Telecom provider

University

ACTION FIELDS:

Reverse direction: The player must change the direction in the next round.

Go back: The player must move 1 cell backwards.

Taxi: The player can move up to 5 cells proceeding the same direction.

Bonus: The player gets 3 points when reaching this field.

Data breach: The player gets a penalty if he/she reaches this field: 5 points will be deducted.

Refund: The player will get 40% extra points of his/her current balance.

Go to start: The player must start the game from the beginning, without losing the points collected so far.

Metro: The player can go to any field in the next round

Roll again: The player can launch the dice again and hence play a second round.

Maxi bonus: The player will gain 10 extra points that can be used in the next rounds.

Personal data infringement penalty: The player will lose 10 points.

CHALLENGE CARDS:

GREEN cards - 1 min for the presentation of the solution + 1 min Q&A

BLUE cards - 2 min for the presentation of the solution + 2 min Q&A

RED cards - 3 min for the presentation of the solution + 3 min Q&A

BONUS CARDS:

Tier 1 (Green)

Gain 1 point

Gain a 10% bonus on the current points

Gain 10% extra on the next bonus from the action fields

Tier 2 (Blue)

Gain 2 point

Gain a 25% bonus on the current points

Gain 30% extra on the next bonus from the action fields

Tier 3 (Red)

Gain 3 point (+1 extra point to the team members)

Gain a 40% bonus on the current points

Gain 50% extra on the next bonus from the action fields

PENALTY CARDS:

Tier 1 (Green)

Lose 1 point

Give 1 point to another player

Move 1 cell back

Tier 2 (Blue)

Lose 2 point

Give 2 points to another player

Move 3 cells back

Tier 3 (Red)

Lose 3 point (-1 point to the team members)

Give 3 points to another player

Move 5 cells back

For non-engaging players:

No points awarded in case challenges are solved by another team member

Skip 1, 2, 3 rounds

Lose 1, 3, 5 points